

PREVALENCE AND ASSOCIATED FACTORS OF WORK RELATED MUSCULOSKELETAL DISORDERS AMONG TEA INDUSTRY WORKERS IN KIRIELLA DIVISIONAL SECRETARIAT OF SRI LANKA

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ABSTRACT

Work related musculoskeletal disorders (WMSD) are common in tea industry workers (TIW). Tea is a main agricultural product and many Sri Lankan people are take part in industry. This study was conducted in order to find the prevalence and associated factors for WMSD in TIW in Kirriella divison. This was descriptive cross sectional study using 350 subjects. Subjects consisted with three occupation categories. The categories were tea leaves pluckers, tea factory workers and tea plantation workers. The data was collected using pre tested interviewer administered socio-demographic questionnaire and interviewer administered stranded Nordic musculoskeletal questionnaire. Data was collected at the working environment of TIW. Data was collected on last seven days and last twelve months of WMSD. The pain was considered as an indicator to WMSD. The most severe or the most discomfort pain was recorded. For the last seven days period upper back pain was the most common pain and elbow pain was the least common pain in TIW. For the last twelve month period upper back pain was the pain with highest prevalence and the hand/wrist pain was the pain with lowest prevalence in TIW. In 95% confidence interval working duration, low water intake, less sleeping hours and non-communicable diseases showed significant association to WMSD among TIW.

KEYWORDS: Back pain, Non-communicable diseases, Tea industry workers, Wrist pain, Work related musculoskeletal disorders.

INTRODUCTION

Tea is a main agricultural product of Sri Lanka. The tea industry dates back to the early 1800's. Tea gardens were introduced by the British. There are several components to the tea powder preparing in both tea gardens and tea factories. These components are mainly based on the human power of tea industry workers (TIW). Duties and responsibilities become different according to the working environment. From them, tea plantation manual laborers or tea garden workers are engaged in land preparation work. Manual laborers or tea factory workers in tea factories are involved in tea processing. Tea pickers participate in picking tea leaves (Sri Lanka export development board, 2016).

The available evidence highlights several points when considering the health of agricultural/industrial workers and the workforce. There are two main types of health problems. These are general health issues and occupational health issues. A general health problem is a health problem that affects the general health of a person. Occupational health problems are health problems caused by occupation. Infectious diseases, agricultural accidents, pesticide poisoning, physical hazards and work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WMSD) and snake bites are examples when considering occupational health issues for agricultural workers (Lim, 1983). Occupational health issues when it comes to industrial work settings can be loud noises, accidents and weapons of mass destruction. Consequently, WMSD have become a

major occupational health problem in agricultural and industrial work settings.

WMSD can be classified as one of the non-communicable diseases. It can be described as a disturbance or discomfort of the musculoskeletal system, peripheral nerves, and neurovascular system in workers resulting from prolonged exposure to workplace hazards and ergonomic malpractice. As a result, even small or simple movements often become difficult and painful. In addition to this, the prevalence of WMSD is highly influenced by restrictive posture, repetitive and static work, vibration, and adverse psychological and social conditions during manual labor (Waters et al, 2007).

The duties of (TIW) lead them to perform many unsafe movements such as full lifting with force, twisting/bending the torso with or without weight, carrying weights on the head/shoulders and upper Use your back, upper and lower body. They must also maintain unconventional postures during working hours (Mania et al, 2012). In addition to these types of musculoskeletal stressors, they may also have to work in harsh environmental conditions, such as bad weather, uneven ground, and frequent changes in the composition of the crew. Beyond that, the task is often performed to meet production and seasonal deadlines without proper rest or recovery time to TIW.

Tissue micro-trauma is the first step in WMSD. Micro-trauma is the result of performing repetitive and/or difficult tasks. This mechanical tissue injury can lead to local and systemic inflammation followed by fibrosis and structural tissue changes. This pathophysiological process leads to WMSD. Therefore, WMSD can be considered an overuse injury (Marry & Ann, 2008). Pain can be considered the primary symptom or symptom of injury to any part of the body. Therefore, work-related musculoskeletal pain (WMSP) can be considered as one of the main indicators of WMSD. WMSP can be used not only to identify WMSD, but also to assess prognosis for WMSD treatment and rehabilitation programs.

In Sri Lanka less amount of scientific studies have been done in this aspect. Therefore, this study will help to fill the knowledge gap on WMSD in Sri Lanka. The main objective of this study was to determine the prevalence and associated factors of WMSD in TIW.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study was a descriptive cross sectional study conducted at two industrial tea plantations of Kiriella secretary division, Rathnapura district. Simple random sampling method was used in the study. Data collection was done for three months period of time. The study sample was 350 tea industry workers (TIW)

from the two industrial plantations. Both males and females were selected to the study between 30 -70 years. Subjects should have been working in tea industry more than 5 years and they could be tea factory worker (TFW), tea plantaion worker (TPW) or tea leaves plucker (TLP).Subjects who was hospitalized more than 7 days with in last three months to the commencing day of the study were not included.

Informed consent was obtained from the eligible candidates after full explanation about the study. Data collection was done at the working environment of TIW using three interviewer administered questionnaires. Socio demographic characteristics and associated factors for WMSP was recorded using pre tested socio-demographic questionnaire. Data on WMSP was recorded using Stranded Nordic questionnaire (SNQ) (Kournika, 1987). From SNQ, data of WMSP in last 12-month period, last seven-day period and the social support and job demand were collected. Data on daily water intake, daily sleeping hours, medical diagnosed non-communicable diseases, alcohol consumption, and betel chewing and smoking were recorded by pre tested health characteristic questionnaires. Data of health characteristic questionnaire was kept blind from recorded data of SNQ. Tea leaves pluckers, tea factory workers and tea plantation workers were considered as main three types of TIW.

RESULTS

There was a 100% respond rate. The study population was consisted with 48.98% females and 51.02% males. When considered about the TLP (n=123) group there were no male subjected recorded. In TFW (n=116), 81.63% male subjects and 18.37% female subjects were recorded. There were 76.09% male subjects and 23.91% female subjects in TPW (n=111) group. Sinhalese and the Sri Lankan Tamils (SLT) were the main two ethnicities in the study. There were 64.63% Sinhalese and 35.37% SLT in the study. In male group there were 66.67% Sinhalese and 33.37% SLT. In female group there were 34.72 % Sinhalese and 65.28% SLT. The mean age of the study population was 50.33±8.13 years. In female population mean age was 50.08±5.99 years. In male population, it was 51.81±7.21 years.

Health characteristics of study population

Data on self reported daily water intake, self reported sleeping hours per a day and the prevalence of non-communicable diseases among study population was collected.

Water intake and sleep

Table 01: Daily water intake and amount of sleeping hours among the study population.

Characteristic	TLF	TFW	TPW
Self reported daily water intake (litters)	2.20±0.70	2.06±0.67	2.04±0.63
Self reported sleeping hours per a day	6.44±0.62	6.30±0.54	6.11±0.58

Prevalence of non-communicable diseases

The prevalence of coronary artery disease, dyslipidemia, hypertension, diabetes mellitus and

bronchial asthma among the study population was recorded.

Table 02: Prevalence of non-communicable diseases among the study population.

Medical Condition	Prevalence		
Coronary Artery Disease	4.86%	5.23%	5.02%
Dyslipidemia	18.74%	19.33%	20.12%
Hypertension	18.23%	15.37%	16.49%
Diabetes mellitus	6.45%	5.33%	7.92%
Bronchial Asthma	2.23%	0.45%	1.34%

Prevalence of WMSP

The pain or the discomfort in major joints in the body was recorded using SNQ. The pain or the discomfort will be taken as an indication for WMSP.

Up to the duration of last twelve months at the date of data collection

The most severe or the most disturbing pain or discomfort in musculoskeletal system, which was experienced within last twelve months by subjects of all three occupations were recorded.

Up to the duration of the last seven days at the date of data collection

The most severe or the most disturbing pain or discomfort in musculoskeletal system, which was experienced within last seven days by subjects of all three occupations were recorded.

Table 03: Pain record for last seven days.

Joint/Body Area	TLF	TFW	TPW
Neck	12.22%	7.21%	5.5%
Shoulder			
1.Left Shoulder	3.45%	5.76%	5.45%
2.Right Shoulder	8.39%	4.38%	3.88%
3.Both Shoulders	2.44%	1.24%	1.23%
Elbow			
1.Left Elbow	6.45%	4.45%	1.76%
2.Right Elbow	4.34%	3.89%	2.23%
3.Both Elbows	3.47%	0%	1.68%
Hand/Wrist			
1.Left Wrist/Hand	3.45%	1.41%	2.34%
2.Right Wrist/Hand	5.89%	1.33%	1.67%
3.Both Wrists/Hands	4.98%	2.60%	1.78%
Upper Back	13.35%	14.76%	29.89%
Lower Back	9.4%	19.13%	20.34%
Buttocks/Hips	2.45%	6.37%	3.44%
One or Both Knees	8.94%	18.13%	10.38%
One or Both Legs	10.87%	9.61%	8.43%

Table 04: Pain records for last twelve months.

Joint/Body Area	TLP	TFW	TPW
Neck	7.47%	1.23%	9.44%
Shoulder			
1.Left Shoulder	11.44%	3.66%	5.39%
2.Right Shoulder	10.37%	4.78%	5.77%
3.Both Shoulders	5.49%	3.99%	2.14%
Elbow			
1.Left Elbow	3.78%	6.19%	3.40%
2.Right Elbow	2.23%	1.43%	2.44%
3.Both Elbows	0.43%	1.22%	3.12%
Hand/Wrist			
1.Left Wrist/Hand	5.21%	2.98%	1.76%
2.Right Wrist/Hand	6.33%	1.45%	0.98%
3.Both Wrists/Hands	4.13%	1.07%	2.2%
Upper Back	18.39%	12.47%	10.72%
Lower Back	11.87%	19.93%	9.56%
Buttocks/Hips	7.70%	5.36%	13.44%
One or Both Knees	12.34%	9.39%	10.46%
One or Both Legs	2.55%	3.58%	7.23%

Social support and job demand

The workplace characteristics, social support and job demand of study subjects were recorded.

Table 05: The workplace characteristics, social support and job demand among the study population.

Statement	Always	Sometimes	Never
I work under extensive work pressure	46.56%	33.57%	19.87%
I have no enough time to finish my job task	24.57%	72.39%	2.5%
At work I speed task on time	21.24%	58.87%	20.19%
I find my work task difficult	73.4%	24.81%	1.79%
I have too many job tasks	64.87%	10.47%	24.66%
The work flow goes smoothly	11.23%	38.77%	60%
I can ask and enquire my work	24.39%	18.05%	57.56%
My work task depend on other colleagues	100%	0%	0%
My work atmosphere is comfortable	30.19%	17.25%	52.56%
If I made a mistake in my work, I find support from my colleagues	84.71%	9.89%	5.4%
If I made a mistake in my work ,I find support from my supervisors	9.4%	21.27%	69.33%
My colleagues are friendly	34.8%	33.69%	31.51%

Factors associated with WMSD

TLP group

The association of daily working duration (p=0.032), self-reported sleeping duration, non-communicable diseases (p=0.012), self-reported daily water intake, alcohol consumption, betel chewing and smoking with WMSD were analyzed using linear regression.

TFW group

The association of daily working duration (p=0.021), self-reported sleeping duration, non-communicable diseases, self-reported daily water intake (p =0.044), alcohol consumption, betel chewing and smoking with WMSDs were analyzed using linear regression.

TPW group

The association of daily working duration, self-reported sleeping duration (p=0.034), non-communicable diseases, self-reported daily water intake, alcohol consumption, betel chewing and smoking with WMSDs were analyzed using linear regression.

Whole TIW group

The association of daily working duration(p=0.024), self-reported sleeping duration(p=0.012), non-communicable diseases, self-reported daily water intake, alcohol consumption, betel chewing and smoking among the whole TIW population with WMSDs were analyzed using linear regression.

DISCUSSION

Socio-demographic characteristics of TIW

The study population was consisted with 48.98% females and 51.02% males. These percentages goes parallel with the gender distribution of Sri Lanka by having close percentages in between 49% and 51%. But the male population in the study is higher than the female population, which is opposite to the current Sri Lankan gender distribution where the female population is higher than the male population. There are only two ethnic groups in this study. Those are Sinhalese and SLT. Study population goes parallel to the ethnic profile of Sri Lanka by having high Sinhalese in comparison to SLT (United Nations statistics division, 2021). The mean age of the study population is 50.33+8.13 years. And it is under the 65 years old which is the retirement age of Sri Lankan employees (Department of Census and Statistics –Sri Lanka, 2022). This will improve the quality of the study by obtaining more accurate employee profile.

Prevalence of WMSP of TIW

In this study data was only collected on WMSP with in last week and last year. It covers both acute and chronic musculoskeletal pains.

Last seven days

When considering about the TLP group prevalence of upper back pain was high compared to other joints of the musculoskeletal system. Hip/buttock pain was least prevalence of pain among TLP. In TFW group lower back pain was the dominant pain and the shoulder pain was the pain with lowest prevalence. Upper back pain was the highest prevalence and the shoulder pain was the lowest prevalence type of pain TPW group. When considering about the whole study population Upper back pain represents the highest prevalence and elbow pain was the lowest prevalence.

Last twelve months

When considering about the TLP group, knee pain was the most common pain and elbow pain was the pain with lowest prevalence of pain. In TFW group lower back pain was the highest prevalence and neck pain was the lowest one. Hip/buttock pain was the pain with high prevalence and wrist/hand pain was the pain with low prevalence in TPW group. When considering the whole study population, upper back pain was the dominant pain and wrist/hand pain was the pain with lowest prevalence.

These results of the study goes opposite with a recent Sri Lankan study in which the lower back pain was most commonest body pain among tea pluckers (Chandarsekara et al., 2020). The studies have been conducted in Indian context brought their results by mentioning lower limb pains are the commonest type of pains in tea workers (Nuridayah et al,2017).

According to results of the study chronic pain shows high prevalence lower limbs and back region. Hence in chronic stage WMSP are common in lower limb and back. This result goes parallel with recent evidence on WMSP in manual workers. In acute type pains back again possess the highest prevalence of pain. In both acute and chronic stages upper limbs or neck don't show significant contribution to WMSP (De Marco, 1996). These results of the study are confirmed by several scientific studies done on WMSP (Fethke et al., 2015).

Factors associated with WMSD

Health characteristics

The daily water intake for males should be 3.7 litters and 2.7 litters for females (US National Academy of Sciences, Engineering and Medicine, 2022). But the daily water intake of study population is less than that value in all TLP, TFW and TPW groups. Having a daily water intake less than the recommended level results in several health problems. These health related problems include several musculoskeletal problems. Due to less amount of the body water muscles can be extremely sensitive. That will cause pains, involuntary muscle contractions and muscle spasms .Less amount of cellular water will results in problems in removing cellular wastes. It will aggravate the inflammation. Inflammation will results in pain and aggravating pains in already affected muscles and joints with other pathologies (World health organization, 2020). Hence the musculoskeletal pains or discomfort experienced may have an influence of low daily water intake.

The recommended sleep for adults is more than 7 hours per day (Nathaniel et.al, 2015). But the results of the study states less than 6.5 hours of daily sleep in all three groups. Disturbed or low sleep results in both chronic regional and chronic widespread musculoskeletal pains (Lee et.al, 2014). Hence the less daily sleeping hour of subjects of the study may results in chronic pains in their musculoskeletal system. And it may aggravate the pain and discomfort of already affected muscles and joints with other primary pathologies (Victore et. al. 2021).

Results of the study shows a high alcohol consumption among the subject of the study. Several studies have suggested that the alcohol consumption may results in aggravating the pain in already existing joint problems as it aggravates the inflammation inside the body (Guntter & Harris, 2019). But several other studies shows that there is no relationship between aggravating joint pains and alcohol consumption (Alexopaluse et al, 2006). There is also a considerable prevalence of smoking among the study population. Evidences have suggested that the smoking shows an association to low back pain (Daniela & Enrico, 2008)

and chronic pain syndrome even in female population (Fethke et al., 2015). Hence the smoking may results in giving both acute and chronic pains to subjects of the study. Even though there is a high prevalence of betel chewing among the study population, there is no any clear evidence to support that betel chewing has an association with WMSPs. Betel chewing may results in pathologies related to temporo-mandibular joint (Micheal et al., 2011). But in this study, data is not collected related to that joint.

When considering about the prevalence of non-communicable diseases, the results of the study goes parallel with non-communicable disease profile of Sri Lanka (Ministry of Health-SL, 2021). Even though there is less amount evidence to support an association or a relationship between non-communicable diseases and WMSP or muscle pains the general health of a person can be compromised by non-communicable diseases. Hence weaken general health can lead to WMSP or chronic pains in musculoskeletal system (Barbeirie et al, 2013).

Work place characteristics

According to the results of the study TIW are working under extensive work pressure and they have to complete their tasks on time. Their work is difficult and sometimes they have to do more than one job task. Those factors may develop work place stress among TIW (Eric, 2006). Work place stress is a subjective psychological factor that affects individually in any given occupation (Andrew, 2003). But in this study data was not collected on work place stress. There for it is unable to find a direct association between level of work place stress and WMSPs. But according to the existing evidence stress at work place may results in giving pains in various regions of musculoskeletal system (Lindega et al, 2014). The back pain becomes a major WMSP due to work related stress in males. But in females, stress doesn't results in back pain (Sven, 2005). According to the results of the study upper back pain and lower back pain are more prevalent in TFW and TPW. In their respective groups gender distribution is nearly 50%. So the results of the study goes slightly parallel with the recent evidences. Work related stress can be further divided in to two parts. They are physical and mental stress. Mental study can be again divided in to emotional stress and cognitive stress. Those types of mental stresses have been considered as a risk factor for developing musculoskeletal pains in shoulders, head and neck by electromyography studies (Rolf et al, 1999). And it also suggests heavy lifting, manual lifting, prolong standing repetitive work tasks are causes for musculoskeletal pains as physical stressors. When considering the manual, goal oriented occupations, psychological stress causes neck and shoulder pains in both males and females (Ulf et al,

1999). Thus physical and mental stress in work place or work related physical and mental stress can be considered as an associate factor for WMSP in study population. But we are unable to find significant evidences on association between work place stress muscle and joint pains in lower limbs. So further scientific studies should be done on that aspect as well.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study on work related musculoskeletal disorders among tea industry workers in Kiriella divisional area, following conclusion can be made.

For the last seven days time period upper back pain was the commonest work related musculoskeletal disorder and the shoulder pain was the lowest disorder.

For the last twelve months period upper back pain was the commonest work related musculoskeletal disorder and the wrist/hand pain was the lowest disorder.

Low water intake, less sleeping hours and heavy work load can be considered associate factors for work related musculoskeletal disorders.

Non-communicable diseases may affect work related musculoskeletal disorders.

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